

Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of diltiazem hydrochloride sustained release matrix tablets

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Abstract:

The matrix tablets were prepared by the direct compression method. Effect of various formulation and processing variables like concentration of HPMC (K100 LV), Eudragit L 100-55, PVAP (Kollidon SR), filler and excipient on stability, buoyancy behavior, dissolution profile, various in-vitro parameters and in-vivo x-ray study were evaluated. Dissolution data was fitted to various pharmacokinetic models to study release pattern of drug from the formulations. The sustained release tablets were then compared to marketed product by using FDA dissolution recommended model independent f2 similarity test.

Formulation with HPMC at 20% and Eudragit L 100-55 at 20% concentration resulted into sustained release matrix tablets that similar to marketed product as per f2 factor similarity test. Formulation with polyvinyl acetate/ povidone and dibasic calcium phosphate at 39.5% level produced sustained release tablets that are similar to marketed product as per f2 factor similarity test guidelines. The dissolution data of all formulations was subjected to pharmacokinetic modeling to study mechanism of drug release and best fit model. It was observed that optimized formulation has followed root of time dependent kinetics for drug release suggesting diffusion controlled release mechanism. Stability studies conducted for long term storage at 25°C and 60%RH of sustained release matrix tablet formulation showed that there were no significant changes in the appearance and dissolution profiles. It was concluded that sustained release diltiazem hydrochloride tablets were developed using HPMC-K100LV in combination with Eudragit L100-55 and PVAP as the release retarding excipients fD11 showed good release. ,

Key words: diltiazem hydrochloride, PVAP (Kollidon SR), HPMC (K100 LV) matrix tablets.

INTRODUCTION

In the present study, Diltiazem hydrochloride is selected as a model drug. Diltiazem is a calcium channel blocker. This drug needs to be administered frequently (usually 3-5 times a day & at night) which makes it a good candidate to formulate as sustained release matrix tablets.

Frequent administration and less bioavailability leads to fluctuations in plasma concentration, sub optimum therapeutic level, less effective management of the disease and less patient compliance. These problems can be solved by formulating drug delivery system of these drugs which will maintain concentration of drug in blood for longer time with controlled release of drug from it. One of the most commonly used methods of modeling drug release is its inclusion within a matrix system.

Matrix systems are extensively used in controlled drug delivery because of its simple and fast producing technology and low cost.

MATERIALS

Diltiazem Hydrochloride Piramal Healthcare Limited, AP(India), Polyvinylalcaetate & Povidone from Glenmark Company, Mumbai, Polymer(PVAP)(Kollidone® SR) from Glenmark Company, Mumbai, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose(HPMC100LV) e, from Glenmark Company, Mumbai, Eudragit® L100-55, from FMC Biopolymer, Ireland, Microcrystalline Cellulose from DMV-Fonterra Excipients(NZ) Ltd, New Zealand, Lactose N.F. from Aptuit Laurus, Hyderabad, Dibasic Calcium Phosphate(Dihydrate) from Aptuit Laurus, Hyderabad, Magnesium Stearate and Colloidal Silicon Dioxide(Aerosil®200) Thomas Baker, Mumbai

METHODOLOGY

Preformulation Study:

Determination of melting point:

Melting points of Diltiazem Hydrochloride and Metoprolol Succinate were determined by capillary method

Solubility:

The solubility of Diltiazem Hydrochloride and Metoprolol Succinate in various media was observed.

Determination of λ max of Diltiazem Hydrochloride and Metoprolol Succinate

Stock solution: Drug in distilled water (100 mg in 100 ml)

Scanning: From the stock solution, a suitable concentration of drug (10 μ g/ml) was prepared in distilled water and UV scan was taken for the above stock solutions between the wavelengths of 200- 400 nm.

Preparation of Calibration Curve

From the 1mg/ml standard solution, a stock solution was prepared to give a concentration of 100 mcg/ml in distilled water. Aliquots of 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0 ml were pipetted out into 10 ml volumetric flask. The volume was made up to the mark with distilled water. These dilutions give 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 μ g/ml.

FTIR Spectroscopy:

The FT-IR spectrum for the obtained gift sample of pure drug was obtained by KBr method and compared with the standard FT-IR spectra.

Formulation table:

Table: Composition of HPMC, Eudragit Matrix Tablet Containing Diltiazem Hydrochloride

Ingredients (mg)	All batches quantity in mg/tablet											
	FD1	FD2	FD3	FD4	FD5	FD6	FD7	FD8	FD9	FD10	FD11	FD12
Diltiazem Hydrochloride	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
HPMC K100LV	45	90	180	270	-	-	-	-	22.5	45	90	135
Eudragit L100-55	-	-	-	-	45	90	180	270	22.5	45	90	135
MCC	155.25	132.75	87.75	42.75	155.25	132.75	87.75	42.75	155.25	132.75	87.75	42.75
Lactose	155.25	132.75	87.75	42.75	155.25	132.75	87.75	42.75	155.25	132.75	87.75	42.75
Magnesium Stearate	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5
Total weight	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450

Table: Composition of PVAP Matrix Tablet Containing Diltiazem Hydrochloride

Ingredients(mg)	All batches quantity in mg/tablet										
	FD13	FD14	FD15	FD16	FD17	FD18	FD19	FD20	FD21	FD22	
Diltiazem Hydrochloride	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	
PVAP	355.50	-	-	177.75	177.75	-	237	59.25	59.25	118.50	
Microcrystalline cellulose	-	355.50	-	177.75	-	177.75	59.25	237	59.25	118.50	
Dibasic Calcium Phosphate dihydrate	-	-	355.50	-	177.75	177.75	59.25	59.25	237	118.50	
Colloidal silicon dioxide	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	
Magnesium Stearate	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	
Total weight	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	

RESULTS

Fourier Transformed Infrared (FT-IR) Spectroscopic Analysis:

Figure : IR spectra of pure diltiazem hydrochloride

Ar-CH str.	3008.41 cm ⁻¹
CH ₃ str.	2838.7 cm ⁻¹
C=O str. (amide)	1685.48 cm ⁻¹
C=O str. (ester)	1743.33 cm ⁻¹
C-S-C str.	1373.07 cm ⁻¹
C-N-C str.	1226.5 cm ⁻¹
C-O-C str.	1029.8 cm ⁻¹

Compatibility Study of HPMC, Eudragit matrix tablet Containing Diltiazem Hydrochloride (FD11)

Figure : IR spectra of pure diltiazem hydrochloride

Ar-CH str.	3008.41 cm ⁻¹
CH ₃ str.	2838.7 cm ⁻¹
C=O str. (amide)	1685.48 cm ⁻¹
C=O str. (ester)	1743.33 cm ⁻¹
C-S-C str.	1373.07 cm ⁻¹
C-N-C str.	1226.5 cm ⁻¹
C-O-C str.	1029.8 cm ⁻¹

Compatibility Study of PVAP matrix tablet containing Diltiazem Hydrochloride.

Figure 25: IR spectra of pure diltiazem hydrochloride

Ar-CH str.	3008.41 cm ⁻¹
CH ₃ str.	2838.7 cm ⁻¹
C=O str. (amide)	1685.48 cm ⁻¹
C=O str. (ester)	1743.33 cm ⁻¹
C-S-C str.	1373.07 cm ⁻¹
C-N-C str.	1226.5 cm ⁻¹
C-O-C str.	1029.8 cm ⁻¹

Figure : IR spectra of mixture of drug (Diltiazem Hydrochloride) and polymers-

FD17

Ar-CH str.	3004.56cm ⁻¹
CH3 str.	2846.42cm ⁻¹
C=O str. (amide)	1685.40cm ⁻¹
C=O str. (ester)	1743.33cm ⁻¹
C-S-C str.	1365.35cm ⁻¹
C-N-C str.	1249.55cm ⁻¹
C-O-C str.	1025.94cm ⁻¹

Evaluation of pre-compression parameters of HPMC, Eudragit SR Matrix Tablet Containing Diltiazem Hydrochloride.

Table No. : Pre-compression evaluation of Formulated HPMC, Eudragit Matrix Tablet.

Formulation	Bulk Density* (g/Cm ³)	Tapped Density* (g/Cm ³)	Compressibility Index* (%)	Hausner Ratio*	Angle of Repose*(^o)
FD1	0.517±0.004	0.564±0.004	8.33±0.021	1.09±0.08	23.62±0.12
FD2	0.510±0.003	0.555±0.002	8.10±0.022	1.08±0.07	23.89±0.26
FD3	0.513±0.006	0.575±0.007	10.78±0.026	1.12±0.10	22.84±0.62
FD4	0.521±0.006	0.564±0.004	7.62±0.020	1.08±0.07	25.64±0.21
FD5	0.500±0.002	0.553±0.002	9.58±0.024	1.10±0.10	21.58±0.15
FD6	0.526±0.004	0.555±0.002	5.22±0.018	1.05±0.05	22.46±0.21
FD7	0.490±0.003	0.565±0.004	13.27±0.031	1.15±0.10	23.76±0.10
FD8	0.516±0.005	0.567±0.004	8.99±0.022	1.09±0.08	25.26±0.20
FD9	0.526±0.006	0.572±0.005	8.04±0.021	1.08±0.07	24.29±0.32
FD10	0.515±0.004	0.566±0.004	9.01±0.022	1.09±0.08	26.48±0.12
FD11	0.515±0.003	0.573±0.005	10.12±0.026	1.11±0.10	22.15±0.21
FD12	0.494±0.004	0.576±0.007	14.23±0.031	1.16±0.11	24.35±0.23

*mean (n = 3)

Evaluation of pre-compression parameters of PVAP SR Matrix Tablet containing Diltiazem Hydrochloride

Table No. : Pre-compression evaluation of Formulated PVAP SR Matrix Tablet

Formulation	Bulk density* (g/cm ³)	Tapped Density* (g/cm ³)	Compressibility Index* (%)	Hausner Ratio*	Angle of Repose* (°)
FD13	0.526±0.006	0.555±0.004	5.22±0.010	1.05±0.04	22.46±0.21
FD14	0.490±0.003	0.565±0.006	13.27±0.230	1.15±0.09	23.76±0.10
FD15	0.516±0.005	0.567±0.004	8.99±0.015	1.09±0.07	25.26±0.20
FD16	0.526±0.006	0.572±0.007	8.07±0.013	1.12±0.08	24.29±0.32
FD17	0.513±0.003	0.575±0.008	10.95±0.024	1.12±0.06	22.84±0.62
FD18	0.513±0.003	0.575±0.008	10.78±0.020	1.12±0.06	22.84±0.62
FD19	0.521±0.004	0.564±0.006	7.62±0.010	1.08±0.05	25.64±0.21
FD20	0.500±0.003	0.553±0.003	9.58±0.024	1.10±0.07	21.58±0.15
FD21	0.526±0.005	0.555±0.003	5.22±0.010	1.05±0.04	22.46±0.21
FD22	0.490±0.002	0.565±0.004	13.27±0.231	1.15±0.08	23.76±0.10

*mean (n = 3)

Evaluation of Post-compression parameters of HPMC and Eudragit Matrix Tablet Containing Diltiazem Hydrochloride.

Table No : Post-compression evaluation of Formulated HPMC, Eudragit SR Matrix Tablet.

Formulation	Hardness* (kg/cm ²)	Weight Variation*(mg)	Friability* %	Content Uniformity (%)
FD1	5.0 ± 0.04	449 ± 2.57	0.80 ± 0.02	98.6 ± 0.05
FD2	5.2 ± 0.05	449 ± 2.28	0.51 ± 0.03	99.5 ± 0.03
FD3	5.2 ± 0.08	448 ± 3.57	0.43 ± 0.02	99.5 ± 0.02
FD4	5.4 ± 0.04	446 ± 2.39	0.42 ± 0.03	97.7 ± 0.03
FD5	4.6 ± 0.04	439 ± 2.13	0.38 ± 0.01	98.5 ± 0.03
FD6	4.8 ± 0.04	441 ± 2.58	0.45 ± 0.01	99.1 ± 0.01
FD7	4.8 ± 0.05	440 ± 2.30	0.30 ± 0.03	98.9 ± 0.07
FD8	5.2 ± 0.08	431 ± 2.58	0.38 ± 0.01	99.0 ± 0.04
FD9	5.2 ± 0.08	449 ± 2.57	0.28 ± 0.01	99.4 ± 0.02
FD10	5.2 ± 0.05	439 ± 2.30	0.40 ± 0.03	99.6 ± 0.02
FD11	5.2 ± 0.07	450 ± 2.47	0.38 ± 0.01	99.8 ± 0.03
FD12	5.4 ± 0.04	439 ± 2.13	0.84 ± 0.02	98.8 ± 0.04
Marketed (DILZEM SR)	5.0 ± 0.08	188 ± 2.57	0.28 ± 0.01	99.4 ± 0.02

*mean (n = 3)

Evaluation of Post-compression parameters of PVAP Matrix Tablet Containing Diltiazem Hydrochloride.

Table No. : Post-compression evaluation of Formulated PVAP SR Matrix Tablet.

Formulation	Hardness* (kg/cm ²)	Weight Variation*(mg)	Friability* (%)	Content Uniformity* (%)
FD13	5.2 ± 0.04	441 ± 2.58	0.45 ± 0.01	98.1 ± 0.01
FD14	4.8 ± 0.04	440 ± 2.30	0.30 ± 0.03	99.4 ± 0.02
FD15	2.2 ± 0.08	431 ± 2.58	All Capped	99.4 ± 0.02
FD16	5.4 ± 0.08	449 ± 2.57	0.28 ± 0.01	99.4 ± 0.02
FD17	5.4 ± 0.08	449 ± 2.58	0.28 ± 0.01	99.4 ± 0.02
FD18	4.6 ± 0.04	449 ± 2.57	0.80 ± 0.02	99.4 ± 0.02
FD19	5.0 ± 0.04	449 ± 2.28	0.51 ± 0.03	97.7 ± 0.03
FD20	5.2 ± 0.05	448 ± 3.57	0.43 ± 0.02	99.4 ± 0.02
FD21	2.8 ± 0.07	446 ± 2.39	All Capped	99.4 ± 0.02
FD22	4.8 ± 0.05	430 ± 2.13	0.38 ± 0.01	99.2 ± 0.03
Marketed	5.0 ± 0.08	188 ± 2.57	0.28 ± 0.01	99.4 ± 0.02
DILZEM SR				

*mean (n = 3)

Time (HRS)	Mean Cumulative % Drug Release of all Formulation (Mean ± SD, n=3)												
	Formulation												M k d
	FD1	FD2	FD3	FD4	FD5	FD6	FD7	FD8	FD9	FD10	FD11	FD12	
1	96.4	52.2	20.22	16.23	98.1	65.5	79.06	60.44	94.4	75.24	28.10	18.25	26.25
2	98.4	82.2	30.12	22.26	98.1	84.6	90.14	73.2	96.5	87.2	42.38	26.27	38.12
3	98.4	90.2	38.21	31.63	98.1	90.7	98.4	80.6	98.4	94.5	53.47	34.62	48.26
4	98.4	94.6	50.14	39.67	98.1	94.7	98.4	86.1	98.4	95.6	62.52	42.64	58.16
5	98.4	97.1	60.23	44.76	98.1	96.6	98.4	88.2	98.4	97.2	71.97	48.77	68.22
6	98.4	99.1	67.92	52.9	98.1	98.2	98.4	94.1	98.4	99.0	78.48	54.9	76.95
7	98.4	99.1	78.44	60.25	98.1	98.2	98.4	98.1	98.4	99.0	84.87	62.2	84.40
8	98.4	99.1	83.8	66.15	98.1	98.2	98.4	98.1	98.4	99.0	89.89	69.1	90.79
9	98.4	99.1	90.43	73.65	98.1	98.2	98.4	98.1	98.4	99.0	95.13	74.6	94.44
10	98.4	99.1	97.35	80.16	98.1	98.2	98.4	98.1	98.4	99.0	96.6	80.2	96.38
11	98.4	99.1	98.43	82.14	98.1	98.2	98.4	98.1	98.4	99.0	98.3	82.1	98.46
12	98.4	99.1	99.22	84.18	98.1	98.2	98.4	98.1	98.4	99.0	99.5	84.1	99.17

Ti (S)	Mean Cumulative % Drug Release of all Formulation (Mean \pm SD, n=3)										
	Formulation										
	FD13	FD14	FD15	FD16	FD17	FD18	FD19	FD20	FD21	FD2	M k d
1	17.24	96.12	98.1	20.3	24.58	98.2	11.63	65.22	98.15	60.2	26.25
2	25.25	98.80	98.8	35.5	40.3	98.8	20.18	86.3	98.9	84.3	38.12
3	31.67	99.11	99.1	44.5	49.8	98.8	22.90	92.8	99.2	92.8	48.26
4	35.60	99.11	99.1	51.8	59.7	98.8	25.30	99.1	99.2	96.1	58.16
5	39.81	99.11	99.1	59.1	69.5	98.8	27.66	99.1	99.2	96.1	68.22
6	42.92	99.11	99.1	65.1	75.6	98.8	28.38	99.1	99.2	96.1	76.95
7	46.30	99.11	99.1	70.9	82.5	98.8	29.93	99.1	99.2	96.1	84.40
8	48.11	99.11	99.1	77.5	88.5	98.8	31.1	99.1	99.2	96.1	90.79
9	49.63	99.11	99.1	83.2	92.9	98.8	31.7	99.1	99.2	96.1	94.44
10	51.15	99.11	99.1	87.5	95.2	98.8	32.45	99.1	99.2	96.1	96.38
11	53.12	99.11	99.1	92.2	97.7	98.8	33.74	99.1	99.2	96.1	98.46
12	54.14	99.11	99.1	95.6	98.2	98.8	34.44	99.1	99.2	96.1	99.17

KINETIC STUDIES

Formu - Lation	Correlation Coefficient [R]					For Krosmeier- Peppas Equation	
	Zero Order	1st Order	Matirx (Higuchi)	Korsmeyer Peppas	Hix. Crow.	Release Exponent [N]	Rate Constant [K]
FD1	0.6720	0.8072	0.9134	0.9065	0.7425	0.0197	96.5946
FD2	0.6795	0.9614	0.9557	0.9384	0.9561	0.3440	57.6164
FD3	0.9509	0.8803	0.9795	0.9918	0.9728	0.6892	19.3749
FD4	0.9711	0.9842	0.9730	0.9953	0.9940	0.7142	14.9072
FD5	0.8367	0.8574	0.9562	0.3333	0.8432	0.0002	98.0932
FD6	0.5091	0.9132	0.9203	0.9524	0.8763	0.2211	68.7400
FD7	0.8117	0.9695	0.9686	0.9840	0.9600	0.1979	78.9213
FD8	0.5217	0.9200	0.9335	0.9896	0.9072	0.2416	61.1373
FD9	0.6892	0.9028	0.9203	0.8790	0.8259	0.0369	94.2938
FD10	0.3066	0.9617	0.8810	0.9694	0.8432	0.1519	77.1085
FD11	0.8303	0.9363	0.9927	0.9906	0.9919	0.5208	29.6589
FD12	0.9481	0.9875	0.9823	0.9911	0.9907	0.6514	17.3922
Marketed DILZEM SR	0.8763	0.9126	0.9910	0.9901	0.9888	0.5675	26.4660

Formulation	Correlation Coefficient [R]					For Krosmeier-Peppas Equation	
	Zero Order	1st Order	Matrix (Higuchi)	Korsmeyer Peppas	Hix. Crow.	Release Exponent [n]	Rate Constant [k]
FD13	0.7385	0.8725	0.9825	0.9875	0.8360	0.4587	18.4191
FD14	0.6806	0.9073	0.9171	0.9617	0.7991	0.0293	96.3129
FD15	0.6633	0.7893	0.9095	0.8830	0.7219	0.0093	98.1200
FD16	0.9165	0.9630	0.9931	0.9927	0.9914	0.6072	21.9132
FD17	0.8627	0.9651	0.9928	0.9891	0.9927	0.5651	26.4844
FD18	0.6602	0.7683	0.9081	0.9339	0.7033	0.0060	98.2509
FD19	0.5494	0.6870	0.9560	0.9641	0.6472	0.3988	13.7884
FD20	0.7977	0.9611	0.9762	0.9811	0.9782	0.3014	66.7768
FD21	0.6638	0.8053	0.9097	0.9453	0.7281	0.0098	98.1710
FD22	0.7239	0.9842	0.9635	0.9609	0.9589	0.3084	63.4358
Marketed DILZEM SR	0.8763	0.9126	0.9910	0.9901	0.9888	0.5675	26.4660

DSC thermogram of Diltiazem Hydrochloride

DSC thermogram of Diltiazem Hydrochloride and excipients.

CONCLUSION

From the complete study, it is concluded that, HPMC K100LV & Eudragit® L100-55 at a concentration of 20% respectively produced sustained release Diltiazem hydrochloride matrix tablets that are similar to the marketed product (Dilzem SR) in-vitro according to the f2 similarity factor. PVAP & dibasic calcium phosphate at a concentration of 39.5% respectively, produced sustained release Diltiazem hydrochloride matrix tablets that are similar to the marketed product (Dilzem SR) in vitro according to the f2 similarity factor. Under long term storage conditions at 25°C and 60% RH, stability testing performed on the selected HPMC/Eudragit and PVAP tablets showed no significant change in the dissolution rates. Based on this finding, the recommended storage conditions are 25°C and 60% RH. Based on the above, it is concluded that sustained release Diltiazem hydrochloride matrix tablets were developed using HPMC and Eudragit combination and PVAP as the release sustaining excipients. In vitro testing indicated that sustained release Diltiazem hydrochloride matrix tablets had similar dissolution behavior to the marketed product according to the model independent FDA guideline (f2 factor).

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